

NEW ADOPTED DIGITAL ANTITRUST POLICY FRAMEWORK

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Antitrust policy has been changing, but as technology advances, digital framework of the policy needs to be evolved. It is a good idea to double-check adjustments that reflect reality every now and again.

The digital world is growing at a rate that most antitrust agencies challenge to keep up with.

We all know that, over the past few years, the European Commission has pursued numerous competition policy actions against U.S. technology giants. The Commission has frequently claimed that digital platforms that offer their own services and products on their platforms may be anticompetitive. For example, Amazon might sell branded Amazon merchandise alongside other brands' merchandise on Amazon's marketplace, while Netflix streams its own content via Netflix.

The European Commission's so-called "**P2B Regulation**" (*Platform-to-business Regulation*) of 2019 now requires digital platforms to disclose selection and ranking processes of goods and services on their platforms.

The European Commission and various member states are actively working to expand their antitrust powers. These ideas have been circulating in Europe for some time and were summarized in a 2019 Commission expert group report, "**Competition policy for the digital era**," which argued that "dominant digital firms" are likely to have "strong incentives to engage in anti-competitive behavior" and "require vigorous competition policy enforcement and justify adjustments to the way competition law is applied."

Similarly, Germany and France, followed by their allies Italy, Austria, Poland and Spain – the leading advocates of tougher competition policy enforcement in the technology sector. In 2018, German experts drew up "**Competition Law 4.0**," a document that calls for "contestability of positions of power in the digital economy".

The global spread of the coronavirus has increased the demand for e-commerce among the world's population. As a result, the online trading system is growing every year.

A United Nations' study, released in 2021, shows that online sales accounted for 19% of overall retail sales in 2020, up from 16% in 2019 as lockdowns to combat the spread of the coronavirus pandemic fuelled a boom in e-commerce. As for countries, in that period, such as South Korea reported the

highest share at 25.9%, followed by China with a 24.9% share, Britain with 23.3% and the United States with 14.0%.

In Uzbekistan, the volume of e-commerce **grew by 80%** in 2020 alone, compared to previous year.

Additionally, at the beginning of 2022, the number of active UZ domains was 98.945, as of today (October 4) it is 108.159 that has increased by 9% in 10 months.

Reflecting these trends, in Uzbekistan has adopted new **Law “On Electronic Commerce”**. It helps to establish transparent and open direct contractual relations between sellers and buyers, to create a technological market infrastructure that meets international standards soon.

Additionally, to recognize the dominant position and superior negotiating power of the digital platform operator and determine actions that lead to restriction of competition and (or) discrimination of the rights and legal interests of consumers and other business entities, **new regulation has adopted.**

According to new regulation digital platforms can be in the following form:

- electronic trading platforms (marketplaces);
- public procurement and service platforms;
- aggregators (intermediaries) that enable end users to use the services of business users;
- general or targeted online search engines;
- online maps;
- news aggregators;
- platforms for online transmission or sharing of video (including television and film) and audio (including music) content;
- platforms for using or sharing files in different formats;
- social networks;
- aggregators of online self-employed (freelancing) services;
- online collective financing (crowdfunding) platforms;
- online payment systems;
- crypto asset exchange platforms;
- software (mobile applications) for interpersonal online communication without the use of telephone or mobile numbers, including video communication services;
- services based on cloud technologies;
- operating systems;

mobile app stores;
online advertising services;
web browsers;
virtual assistants;
platforms based on artificial intelligence.

According to paragraph 8 Chapter 2, a digital platform operator is recognized as having a dominant position when one of the following conditions is met and there is a direct and indirect network effect a) within the boundaries of the digital space, the amount of revenue of the digital platform operator in the last calendar year, if the digital platform operator has not completed a year since the start of its activity, then the amount of income for the period up to the time of the analysis is one hundred thousand of the amounts of the base calculation equal to or greater than, b) if the total average number of active end users of the digital platform is at least fifty thousand per month or the average number of active business users is at least three thousand per month.

Along with low quantitative criteria boundaries, there is obligation for digital platform operators to approve terms and conditions for customers with the Antimonopoly Committee.

Consequently, it will still challenges regulating possible anticompetitive actions and abuse of dominant position in digital market.

Therefore, it was a necessity to add amendments to digital antitrust framework in current Regulation.

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